

Just Energy Transition: Modelling the Shift from Hydro Dependency to a Balanced Energy Mix Using OSeMOSYS

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The energy sector plays a pivotal role in driving economic and human development, and Zambia is no exception. The Government of the Republic of Zambia (GRZ) has set an ambitious agenda for economic diversification and industrialisation, aiming to transform Zambia into a prosperous middle-income country with diversified income sources and universal electricity access. This vision includes increasing refined copper production to 3 million tonnes per year, expanding mining activities, transforming agriculture for mass production and export, electrifying urban and intercity rail transport, and establishing industrial zones for local mineral beneficiation. Equally important is the commitment to achieving universal electricity access by 2030 through a combination of grid and off-grid solutions.

Zambia's current installed electricity generation capacity is 3,811 MW, with hydropower contributing around 85%, underscoring a heavy dependence on water resources. However, climate change-induced droughts have increasingly constrained the ability to meet both existing and future energy demand.

Despite abundant renewable resources—particularly hydro and solar—many regions, especially Northern and Luapula Provinces, still lack reliable electricity access. These areas suffer from insufficient baseload capacity due to undeveloped hydro potential. Grid expansion is slow, hindered by aging infrastructure and limited public financing.

Using the OSeMOSYS model, three scenarios were explored: Business-as-Usual (BAU), Increased Solar Generation (ISG), and a Decarbonized Energy Mix (DEM).

KEYWORDS

Energy, Solar, Hydro Power, Electricity, Energy Modelling, OseMOSYS, Renewable, Climate, Transition

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1. INTRODUCTION

In line with Zambia's Integrated Resource Plan (IRP) which is a comprehensive, long-term strategy for the nation's power sector, aiming to address challenges and establish a reliable and cost-effective electricity framework. Designed with a forward-looking vision until 2050, with a focal point on the period leading up to 2030. The IRP addresses Zambia's full electricity landscape, addressing power demand, generation, transmission, distribution, and off-grid access, thereby developing a roadmap for a robust, resilient, and sustainable energy future that aligns with Zambia's developmental aspirations.

While focusing mostly on the on-grid sector, the IRP incorporates recommendations for off-grid solutions where appropriate, highlighting the least cost approach for inclusive energy access. This approach embraces grid expansion, mini-grids, and standalone solar systems, allowing the IRP to harmoniously support the vision 2030 universal access.

It is against this background that this report seeks to investigate Zambia's complex energy landscape, examining its key challenges and potential mitigation measures—particularly in response to the climate induced drought port is guided by two central research questions:

- i. How can increased investment in solar power generation help alleviate the country's current dependency to hydroelectricity?
- ii. How can a just energy transition towards a balanced energy mix enhance national energy security and supply reliability?

2. METHODOLOGY

The Starter Data Kit (SDK) provided the foundation for developing the Zambian energy sector reference model. It included calibrated primary energy sources and accounted for the residual capacities of existing power generation technologies, forming the backbone upon which the team built the models and explored the 3 aforementioned scenarios.

However, strategic energy planning is needed to evaluate the trade-offs between grid-based expansion, decentralized options, and investment in new baseload capacity. OseMOSYS (MUIO 5) was chosen as the software for medium- and long-term analysis. Also ensuring adherence to Green House Gas (GHG) restrictions, and enhanced energy technology mix and other constraints. The following were the scenarios investigated in the Zambian context:

In the Business-as-Usual (BAU) scenario, hydropower remains the dominant generation source, reflecting the current energy mix and ongoing efforts to exploit Zambia’s estimated 6 GW hydropower potential in the Northern region. In the Increased Solar Generation (ISG) scenario, the model incorporates national targets to install 3 GW of solar PV by 2030, in line with the Integrated Resource Plan (IRP), and to reach 5 GW by 2050. The Decarbonization Energy Mix (DEM) scenario applies a 30% greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions reduction constraint, limiting coal-fired generation to support emissions cuts in alignment with the National Energy Policy and the IRP

3. RESULTS

As electricity needs grow in line with planned economic development, the country’s generation capacity is also expected to expand. This growth is primarily driven by increased energy use in the mining and agricultural sectors, rising population, and efforts to meet residential electrification goals. In addition, national development priorities, such as achieving universal access to electricity, advancing industrialization, and promoting regional power trade are key factors influencing the expansion of generation capacity.

- **Production by Technology Mode**

The results across all scenarios indicate a steady increase in electricity generation across all scenarios. In the BAU scenario, total production

reaches 170 PJ, largely sustained by existing hydropower and residual solar capacity. The ISG scenario shows a significant increase to 250 PJ, driven by higher installed capacities in solar PV and coal, aligned with national solar targets. In the DEM scenario, generation rises further to 350 PJ, reflecting the integration of geothermal and expanded solar capacity, while coal use is constrained to meet a 30% GHG emissions reduction target. Overall, growth in electricity generation is attributed to investments in new power plants and rising electricity consumption, particularly from the mining sector and residential sector to attain universal access to electricity.

Figure 1 shows the results on production by technology mode across all three scenarios

- **Accumulated New Capacity**

The accumulated new electricity generation capacity increases from 16 GW in the BAU scenario to 25 GW in ISG, and approximately 49 GW in the DEM scenario. This growth is largely driven by rising electricity demand across economic sectors—particularly the residential and industrial sectors. At the residential level, the push to achieve universal electricity access is a key driver, while in the industrial sector, expanding copper production demands greater energy inputs.

Figure 2 shows results in comparison

In the BAU scenario, new capacity is primarily a modest expansion of hydropower, optimized by the model. In ISG, new capacity is dominated by solar energy, aligned with the national target of 3 GW of installed solar generation. The DEM scenario continues this solar expansion but also integrates geothermal energy, which provides the necessary baseload for solar integration substituting the coal and oil.

- **Annualized Investment Cost**

The Investment required for BAU, ISG&GE and DEM are illustrated in the figure 3 below:

- **Emissions by Technology**

Greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by technology are assessed across all scenarios in the model. Of the three, only the DEM scenario applies a 30% GHG emissions reduction constraint. In this scenario, coal capacity is limited to support a targeted 30% reduction in power sector emissions, aligned with the National Energy Policy and Integrated Resource Plan (IRP).

Figure 4 shows the reduction in emission per scenario from all GHG emitting technologies:

In the BAU scenario, there is no emissions constraint, but the measured emissions generated by existing coal plants which will be phased out by 2040 due to the end of its operational life. The most important GHG emissions were measured in the ISG scenario. Actually, to ensure grid reliability, the model incorporates coal as a baseload source, resulting in increased emissions due to optimized investments in coal, hydro, and diesel.

In contrast, the DEM scenario enforces the emissions constraint, leading to a significant reduction in coal generation—the largest GHG contributor. To maintain grid reliability and support the integration of variable renewable energy sources (VRES), the model introduces geothermal power as a clean, stable baseload alternative.

4. DISCUSSION

Geothermal energy emerges as a key baseload technology in the DEM scenario, supporting deeper integration of solar while reducing GHG emissions. This shift reduces reliance on hydro and high-emitting coal generation. Solar remains the leading Variable Renewable Energy Source (VRES) in both the ISG and DEM scenarios, aligning with national energy targets.

The findings highlight geothermal exploration and resource mapping as priority areas for government and private sector investment. Given current grid instability, grid modernization is also critical to support VRES integration and improve load management.

However, the study has limitations. Simplified assumptions on cost curves, technology performance, and demand growth may not reflect real-world complexities. The model also overlooks regional disparities in resource access and applies a fixed 30% emissions constraint in DEM, without adapting to evolving international commitments or technological advancements.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, a dynamic and inclusive approach to energy sector reforms—grounded in strategic collaboration with academia, the private sector, and other stakeholders—is essential to enhance energy modeling and planning for country-specific interventions such as green industry, clean transport, and clean cooking initiatives.

In Zambia's context, it's critical to integrate climate risks—such as hydrological variability—into long-term power system models, especially in light of increasing climate-induced droughts.

Ongoing policy reforms have encouraged solar uptake and broader energy investment. However, sustained progress requires more targeted policies, including strategic incentives, standardized Power Purchase Agreements (PPAs), and a liberalized market that fosters innovation and broader participation. These elements are key to achieving energy security, technological advancement, and alignment with the National Energy Policy, Integrated Resource Plan (IRP), and Presidential directives.

Looking ahead, scenario modeling that includes VRES, nuclear, and wind energy should be prioritized. This will demand robust, flexible, and inclusive policy and regulatory frameworks.

Future work should focus on more detailed, dynamic models to better inform policy reforms and enhance the relevance of recommendations.

Finally, there is an urgent need to de-risk early-stage geothermal exploration and expand incentives for VRES deployment to unlock Zambia's full energy potential.

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